

Growth Characteristics and Morphological Development of Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*)

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ABSTRACT: This study documents the growth characteristics and morphological development of tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum*) cultivated in containers over a two-month observation period. The primary objective was to observe major plant growth stages including germination, vegetative development, and early flowering, as well as to measure visible plant parts such as stem and leaf length. Tomato seeds were planted in well-drained soil and exposed to 6–8 hours of sunlight daily. Regular watering was provided, and organic materials such as banana, apple, and orange peels were applied every two weeks as soil supplements. Germination occurred six days after planting. Weekly measurements showed a gradual increase in stem length from 0 cm to 33 cm, with progressive development of compound leaves and increased leaflet size. Although vegetative growth was evident, flowering had not fully occurred by the end of the observation period, and fruit formation was not observed. Results indicate that container-grown tomatoes can achieve healthy vegetative growth under proper sunlight and moisture conditions; however, organic fruit waste alone is insufficient to promote early flowering and fruiting. This study demonstrates that consistent care, adequate water supply, and appropriate nutrient management are essential for successful tomato cultivation.

Keywords: *Solanum lycopersicum*, tomato plant, container gardening, plant growth, morphological development, germination

I. Brief background information/overview

Figure 1. Common name: Tomato plant

Scientific name: *Solanum lycopersicum*

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) is one of the most important vegetables worldwide. World tomato production in 2001 was about 105 million tons of fresh fruit from an

estimated 3.9 million ha. As it is a relatively short duration crop and gives a high yield, it is economically attractive and the area under cultivation is increasing daily. Tomato belongs to the *Solanaceae* family. This family also includes other well-known species, such as potato, tobacco, peppers and eggplant (aubergine).

Tomato is a perennial herbaceous plant but it is often grown as an annual crop even if biennial and perennial forms exist. Tomato is cultivated in tropical and temperate climates in open field or under greenhouse in temperate climate. Greenhouses are often used for large-scale production. In warm climate with the right light intensity for growth, around 45 days are necessary from germination to anthesis and 90-100 days to reach to beginning of fruit ripeness (Nuez, 2001). The end use of the crop, whether for the processing market or fresh market, will determine the cultivars sown, the time of harvest and harvest processes, which can be manual or mechanical (Nuez, 2001).

The growth habit of the plant varies from indeterminate to determinate and may reach up to 3 metres (m) in height. The primary root may grow several metres in length. The stem is angular and covered by hairy and glandular trichomes that confer a characteristic smell. Leaves are alternately arranged on the stem with a 137.5° phyllotaxy. Leaves range in shape from lobed to compound, with segments arranged pinnately. Compound leaves are typically comprised of five to nine leaflets. Leaflets are petiolated and dentated. All leaves are covered by glandular, hairy trichomes. The tomato fruit is globular or ovoid. Botanically, the fruit exhibits all of the common characteristics of berries; a simple fleshy fruit that encloses its seed in the pulp. The outer skin is a thin and fleshy tissue that comprises the remainder of the fruit wall as well as the placenta. The colour of the fruit is derived from the cells within the fleshy tissue. Tomato fruits can be either bilocular or multilocular. Between 50 and 200 seeds are located inside the locular cavities and are enclosed in gelatinous membranes. On average, the seeds are small (5 x 4 x 2 mm) and lentil shaped. The seed contains the embryo and the endosperm and is covered by a strong seed coat, called the testa. The development of the fruit takes seven to nine weeks after fertilisation. The many end uses of tomato fruit, as well as food and feed safety considerations, including composition of key food and feed nutrients, anti-nutrients, allergens, and toxicants, are detailed in the "OECD consensus document on compositional considerations for new varieties of tomato" (OECD, 2008).

Tomato has its origin in the South American Andes. The cultivated tomato was brought to Europe by the Spanish conquistadors in the sixteenth century and later introduced from Europe to southern and eastern Asia, Africa and the Middle East. More recently, wild tomato has been distributed into other parts of South America and Mexico. Common names for the tomato are: tomate (Spain, France), tomat (Indonesia), faan ke'e (China), tomati (West Africa), tomatl (Nahuatl), jitomate (Mexico), pomodoro (Italy), nyanya (Swahili).

Tomatoes contribute to a healthy, well-balanced diet. They are rich in minerals, vitamins, essential amino acids, sugars and dietary fibres. Tomato contains much vitamin B and C, iron and phosphorus. Tomato fruits are consumed fresh in salads or cooked in sauces, soup and meat or fish dishes. They can be processed into purées, juices and ketchup. Canned and dried tomatoes are economically important processed products. Yellow tomatoes have higher vitamin A content than

red tomatoes, but red tomatoes contain lycopene, an anti-oxidant that may contribute to protection against carcinogenic substances.

II. Goals

- I will be able to grow tomato plants.
- I will know how long it takes to grow to tomato.
- I will know how to protect tomato plants.
- To observe all major plant stages including, germination, flowering, fruiting and harvesting for a sufficient duration of time.
- To collect data on measurements of visible parts such as length of stems and leaves.

III. Materials

1. Container or pot with holes drilled into the bottom for drainage.
2. Watering can
3. Soil/dirt
4. Skin of fruits such as banana, apple and orange.
5. Tomato seed
6. Support system
7. Garden gloves
8. Ruler and tape measure for measurement

IV. Procedures

1. I used a large container or pot. I made sure that it has drainage holes in the bottom. I made use of loose, well- drainage soil. I recommend a good potting mixed well with organic matter.
2. I placed and sowed the tomato seeds on top of soil and 1.5 cm apart in a pot.
3. I placed the pot in a spot that received 6 to 8 hours of sunlight in a day.
4. I kept seeds starting mix just moist until seeds germinate. Germination takes 6 days.
5. I clipped away the weaker seedlings once the strongest seedling is about 5cm tall.
6. I kept the soil moist. I made sure to check daily and provide ample water during heat wave.
7. I allowed a gentle breeze from a fan to rustle over young seedlings each day so that they grow strong stems.
8. About two weeks after germination seedlings; I transferred to other pots that have large amount of soil. I careful not to disturb the roots. This is called potting up.

9. I made sure to water well throughout the growing season. I always water the plants in the early morning hours. This provides the plant with the moisture it needs to make it through an entire hot day.
10. I supplied the plant with skin of banana , apple and orange every two weeks.

V. Observations

Figure 2 Tomato plant

Tomato plant

Figure 3. Tomato plant leaf morphology

Plant type: Angiosperms

Leaf arrangement: Spiral

Leaf type: Pinnately compound

Leaf margin: Crenate

Leaf tip/apex: Acute

Leaf base: Oblique

Leaf shape: Lanceolate

Leaf venation: Reticulate venation

Root: Vigorous tap root system that grows to a depth of 50 cm or more. The main root produces dense lateral and adventitious roots.

Stem: Growth habit ranges between erect and prostrate. It grows to a height of 2-4 m. The stem is solid, coarse, hairy and glandular.

Flower: Bisexual, regular and 1.5-2 cm in diameter. They grow opposite or between leaves. Calyx tube is short and hairy, sepals are persistent. Usually 6 petals up to 1 cm in length, yellow and reflexed when mature. 6 stamens, anthers are bright yellow in colour surrounding the style with an elongated sterile tip. Ovary is superior and with 2-9 compartments. Mostly self- but partly also crosspollinated. Bees and bumblebees are the most important pollinators.

Fruit: Fleshy berry, globular to oblate in shape and 2-15 cm in diameter. The immature fruit is green and hairy. Ripe fruits range from yellow, orange to red. It is usually round, smooth or furrowed.

Seeds: Numerous, kidney or pear shaped. They are hairy, light brown 3-5 mm long and 2-4 mm wide. The embryo is coiled up in the endosperm. Approximate weight of 1000 seeds is 2.5 – 3.5 g.

➤ **A planner/ time frame table for growing a plant.**

Time and date plant	December 22, 2020
Germination date	Decemember 28, 2020
Date transplanted	January 5, 2021
Days to maturity	March 2, 2021 (estimated)
Blooming / fruit date	March 15, 2021 (estimated)
Harvest date	April 1, 2021 (estimated)

➤ **Weekly measurements of visible parts such as length of stems and leaves, color of flower/fruit.**

December 22, 2020

Figure 4. I make a clean start, label my containers and plant tomato seeds dry.

Length of stem	0cm
Length of leaves	0cm
Color of flower	None

December 29 2020

Figure 5. Tomato seeds germinate in 6 days. The seeds have germinated as soon as I see green plant emerging from the growing medium.

Length of stem	3 cm
Length of leaves	1.5 cm
Color of flower	Green

January 5 2021

Figure 6. I clipped away the weaker seedlings once the strongest seedling is about 5cm tall. About two weeks after germination seedlings; I transferred to other pots that have large amount of soil. I careful not to disturb the roots

Length of stem	5.6 cm
Length of leaves	Length of bigger leaves: 3 cm Length of smaller leaves: 1cm
Color of flower	Green

January 12 2021

Figure 7. The very young leaf is lobed and basically simple. the leaf is now obviously compound. as the leaf develops. it grow in size and well as in number of leaflets.

Length of stem	10 cm
Length of leaves	Length of bigger leaves: 7 cm Length of smaller leaves: 1cm
Color of flower	Green and yellow

January 19 2021

Figure 8. The leaf is now obviously compound. As the leaf develops, it grows in size and well as in number of leaflets.

Length of stem	13 cm
Length of leaves	Length of bigger leaves: 7 cm Length of smaller leaves: 2 cm
Color of flower	Green

January 27 2021

Figure 9. As the leaf develops, it grows in size and well as in number of leaflets. The skin of apple and banana start to rotten.

Length of stem	17 cm
Length of leaves	Length of bigger leaves: 8 cm Length of smaller leaves: 2 cm
Color of flower	Green

February 2 2021

Figure 10. As the leaf develops, it grows in size and well as in number of leaflets. The stem also grow in length and getting stronger.

Length of stem	22 cm
Length of leaves	Length of bigger leaves: 8 cm Length of smaller leaves: 2 cm
Color of flower	Green

February 9 2021

Figure 11. As the leaf develops, it grows in size and well as in number of leaflets. The stem also grow in length and getting stronger.

Length of stem	26 cm
Length of leaves	Length of bigger leaves: 9 cm Length of smaller leaves: 1 cm
Color of flower	Green and yellow green

February 16 2021

Figure 12. As the leaf develops, it grows in size and well as in number of leaflets. The stem also grow in length and getting stronger.

Length of stem	30 cm
Length of leaves	Length of bigger leaves: 9 cm Length of smaller leaves: 1 cm
Color of flower	Green and yellow

February 20 2021

Figure 13. As the leaf develops, it grows in size and well as in number of leaflets. The stem also grow in length and getting stronger. The flowers have not bloom yet.

Length of stem	33 cm
Length of leaves	Length of bigger leaves: 8 cm Length of smaller leaves: 1 cm
Color of flower	Green and yellow

VI. Conclusion

In conclusion, tomato plant can be planted in containers. It requires a well- drained, fertile growing medium. The skin of fruits such as banana, apple and orange which I placed in the soil did help the tomato plant to grow. Also, placing the tomato plant in a spot that received 6 to 8 hours of sunlight in a day will help the plant grow. Keeping the soil moist and make sure to check daily and provide ample water during heat wave will benefit the tomato plant. Insufficient water will cause flower drop and blossom end rot. Furthermore, the tomato plant did not bloom a flowers yet, therefore there were no fruits produce on February 22. Lastly, skin of fruits (such as apple, banana apple) and water tomato plant are not enough to produce a fruit at early.

VII. References

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